

Cross-Entropy Method Adapted for Evaluating the Teaching Quality of University Physical Education Utilizing 2-Tuple Linguistic Neutrosophic Sets

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Abstract: The evaluation of university physical education teaching quality helps measure the actual effectiveness of the courses and ensures the achievement of teaching objectives. Through evaluation, schools can identify deficiencies in teaching and make improvements, enhancing students' physical fitness and health. Additionally, evaluation provides data support for teaching reforms, aiding in curriculum optimization and strengthening faculty, thereby promoting the comprehensive development of physical education and fostering students' lifelong awareness of fitness and healthy lifestyles. The teaching quality evaluation of university physical education adopts the multiple-attribute group decision-making (MAGDM) approach. Currently, cross-entropy (CE) model was constructed to handle the MAGDM. To capture uncertain data for the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education, 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic numbers (2TLNNs) are administrated as valuable decision tool. This study constructs the 2TLNN cross-entropy (2TLNN-CE) technique, which combines traditional cross-entropy and 2TLNSs. The 2TLNN-CE technique is applied to MAGDM in the context of teaching quality evaluation. Furthermore, numerical example for the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education is presented, and comparative analysis is administrated to validate the advantages of 2TLNN-CE technique. The contributions of this study are summarized:(1) Extension of cross-entropy technique to 2TLNSs, enabling its application in uncertain decision scenarios; (2) Introduction of 2TLNN-CE technique for MAGDM, specifically tailored for teaching quality evaluation; (3) Illustration of 2TLNN-CE technique through numerical example of teaching quality evaluation of university physical education accompanied by comparative analysis to highlight its benefits.

Keywords: Multiple-attribute group decision-making (MAGDM); 2TLNSs; 2TLNN-CE model; teaching quality evaluation

1. Introduction

The quality of university physical education teaching is a crucial standard for measuring the effectiveness of sports courses in higher education, directly impacting students' physical fitness, athletic skills, and health awareness. High-quality physical education requires that the teaching content meets the actual needs of students while also being scientific and systematic, ensuring that students can comprehensively grasp fundamental sports skills and theoretical knowledge. Additionally, diverse and flexible teaching methods are key; teachers should adopt personalized approaches based on students' physical conditions and interests to stimulate their enthusiasm for sports and enhance classroom participation. The quality of teaching is also reflected in student learning outcomes. Through regular assessments and tests, schools can track students' progress in physical education, including improvements in physical fitness, health levels, and mastery of sports skills. Quality physical education not only helps students develop good exercise habits during their time at university but also fosters lifelong awareness of physical activity, promoting a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, improving the quality of university physical education is essential for enhancing overall educational standards and plays a critical role in students' comprehensive development. The earliest research was conducted by Liang [1], who explored how to improve the teaching quality of university martial arts courses through a systematic and standardized teaching model. Liang [1] suggested that martial arts courses not only enhance students' physical fitness but also foster lifelong exercise habits, providing recommendations for the role of universities in promoting martial arts. Following this, Wang and Yan [2] studied the teaching efficacy of university physical education teachers and its impact on teaching quality. They found through surveys that the higher the teachers' sense of efficacy, the better the teaching quality, and proposed strategies to enhance teacher efficacy. Later, Zhang and He [3] proposed a reform plan to quantify and standardize the evaluation criteria for university physical education teaching quality. Their research showed that quantitative evaluation helps improve classroom teaching quality and increases the motivation of both teachers and students. In 2017, Zhou and Wu [4] constructed a satisfaction evaluation model to assess the quality of university physical education teaching. They used the Delphi method and the analytic hierarchy process to propose a satisfaction evaluation system composed of multiple indicators and verified its operability and reliability. Liu [5] pointed out that the deviation in modern university physical education quality evaluation standards is one of the reasons for the decline in students' physical fitness. He highlighted the issues in evaluating physical education quality and proposed strategies to improve classroom teaching. Following this, Wang, Ding and Zhang [6] studied the construction of an information-based teaching quality evaluation system, proposing a multi-level evaluation index system and verifying its scientific and practical applicability through actual courses. In 2020, Liu, Yin and Wang [7] established a university physical education quality assurance system, suggesting measures such as layered teaching, school-based curriculum development, and innovative teaching methods to enhance teaching quality. Their study

provided valuable insights for managing physical education. From the perspective of "students' core sports literacy," Zhao, Gong and Sheng [8] constructed a new classroom teaching quality evaluation system, adding a teaching reflection component and emphasizing the diversification and scientific nature of the evaluation system. In 2022, based on grey system theory and fuzzy evaluation, Zhou and Wang [9] proposed a new model for evaluating university physical education quality. They used the analytic hierarchy process to determine the weight of evaluation standards and suggested strategies to further improve teaching quality. Lastly, Ma [10] explored the standardization reform of university physical education teaching quality evaluation, emphasizing the importance of improving teaching quality through a scientific evaluation system and proposed specific measures for standardization reform.

The teaching quality evaluation of university physical education presents a MAGDM. To address this, the CE technique [11, 12] has been utilized as a means to manage MAGDM. In the context of teaching quality evaluation of university physical education, 2TLNSs [13] are administrated as valuable decision tool to handle uncertain information in light with neutrosophic sets [14-17]. While various techniques have been developed to optimize the traditional cross-entropy technique [18], there is a scarcity of methods that apply the entropy technique [19] and cross-entropy technique [18] to manage MAGDM using 2TLNSs. In this study, we propose the 2TLNN-CE approach, which combines the traditional CE approach along with 2TLNSs. The 2TLNN-CE approach is then applied to MAGDM for teaching quality evaluation of university physical education. To illustrate key advantages of proposed technique, numerical example concerning the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education is presented, accompanied by comparative analysis. The key contributions of this study are summarized: (1) Extension of cross-entropy technique to integrate with 2TLNSs, enhancing its applicability; (2) Development of the 2TLNN-CE technique for MAGDM using 2TLNSs; (3) Demonstration of the 2TLNN-CE technique through a specific numerical study on the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education, with comparisons made against existing techniques. (4) Comparative analysis confirms the effectiveness of 2TLNN-CE technique for teaching quality evaluation of university physical education.

To achieve this, the study follows a fundamental structure outlined: Sect. 2 provides the 2TLNSs. Sect. 3 presents the application of 2TLNN-CE technique for MAGDM. In Sect. 4, numerical example focusing on the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education is presented. Comparative analysis is administrated to further examine the results.

2. Preliminaries

Wang et al. [13] administrated the 2TLNSs.

Definition 1 [20, 21]. Let $ool = \{ool_1, ool_2, \dots, ool_{oo}\}$ be LTSs. The label ool_i is linguistic variable, and ool is administrated:

$$ool = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} ool_0 = \text{extremely poor}, ool_1 = \text{very poor}, ool_2 = \text{poor}, ool_3 = \text{medium}, \\ ool_4 = \text{good}, ool_5 = \text{very good}, ool_6 = \text{extremely good}. \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Definition 2[13]. Let $oos_j (j=1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$ be 2TLSs. If

$oos = \langle (ool_t, oo\xi), (ool_i, oo\psi), (ool_f, oo\zeta) \rangle$ is administrated for $ool_t, ool_i, ool_f \in ool$,

$oo\xi, oo\psi, oo\zeta \in [-0.5, 0.5)$, $(ool_t, oo\xi), (ool_i, oo\psi), (ool_f, oo\zeta)$ is the linguistic truth-

membership, linguistic indeterminacy and linguistic falsity-membership, then the 2TLNSs

are administrated:

$$oos_j = \langle (ool_{t_j}, oo\xi_j), (ool_{i_j}, oo\psi_j), (ool_{f_j}, oo\zeta_j) \rangle \quad (2)$$

with condition $0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_j}, oo\xi_j) \leq oo$, $0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_j}, oo\psi_j) \leq oo$,

$0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_j}, oo\zeta_j) \leq oo$, and

$$0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_j}, oo\xi_j) + \Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_j}, oo\psi_j) + \Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_j}, oo\zeta_j) \leq 3oo.$$

Definition 3[13]. Let $oos = \langle (ool_t, oo\xi), (ool_i, oo\psi), (ool_f, oo\zeta) \rangle$, linguistic score

function $LSF(oos)$ and linguistic accuracy function $LAF(o\delta)$ are

$oos = \langle (ool_t, oo\xi), (ool_i, oo\psi), (ool_f, oo\zeta) \rangle$:

$$LSF(oos) = \frac{(2oo + \Delta^{-1}(ool_t, oo\xi) - \Delta^{-1}(ool_i, oo\psi) - \Delta^{-1}(ool_f, oo\zeta))}{3oo} \quad (3)$$

$$LAF(oos) = \frac{oo + \Delta^{-1}(ool_t, oo\xi) - \Delta^{-1}(ool_f, oo\zeta)}{3oo} \quad (4)$$

Definition 4[13]. Let $oos_1 = \langle (ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1), (ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1), (ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1) \rangle$,

$oos_2 = \langle (ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2), (ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2), (ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2) \rangle$, then (1) If $LSF(oos_1) < LSF(oos_2)$,

$oos_1 < oos_2$; (2) If $LSF(oos_1) = LSF(oos_2)$, $LAF(oos_1) < LAF(oos_2)$, $oos_1 < oos_2$;

(3) If $LSF(oos_1) = LSF(oos_2)$, $LAF(oos_1) = LAF(oos_2)$, $oos_1 = oos_2$;

Definition 5[13]. Let $oos_1 = \left\langle (ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1), (ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1), (ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1) \right\rangle$,

$oos_2 = \left\langle (ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2), (ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2), (ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2) \right\rangle$,

$oos = \left\langle (ool_t, oo\xi), (ool_i, oo\psi), (ool_f, oo\zeta) \right\rangle$, then

$$oos_1 \oplus oos_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1) + \Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2)}{oo} \right) \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1) \cdot \Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2)}{oo} \right) \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1) \cdot \Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2)}{oo} \right) \right) \end{array} \right\};$$

$$oos_1 \otimes oos_2 = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1) \cdot \Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2)}{oo} \right) \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1) + \Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2)}{oo} \right) \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1) + \Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2)}{oo} \right) \right) \end{array} \right\};$$

$$\xi oos = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_t, oo\xi)}{oo} \right)^\xi \right) \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_i, oo\psi)}{oo} \right)^\xi \right), \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_f, oo\zeta)}{oo} \right)^\xi \right) \end{array} \right\}, \xi > 0;$$

$$oos^{\xi} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta \left(oo \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_t, oo\xi)}{oo} \right)^{\xi} \right), \Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_i, oo\psi)}{oo} \right)^{\xi} \right) \right) \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_f, oo\zeta)}{oo} \right)^{\xi} \right) \right) \end{array} \right\}, \xi > 0.$$

Definition 6[13]. Let $oos_j = \left\langle (ool_t, oo\xi_j), (ool_i, oo\psi_j), (ool_f, oo\zeta_j) \right\rangle$, the 2TLNNWG is:

$$\begin{aligned} & 2TLNNWG(oos_1, oos_2, \dots, oos_n) \\ &= (oos_1)^{ow_1} \otimes (oos_2)^{ow_2} \dots \otimes (oos_n)^{ow_n} = \bigotimes_{j=1}^n (oos_j)^{ow_j} \\ &= \left(\begin{array}{l} \Delta \left(oo \prod_{j=1}^n \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_t, oo\xi_j)}{oo} \right)^{ow_j} \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \prod_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_i, oo\psi_j)}{oo} \right)^{ow_j} \right) \right), \\ \Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \prod_{j=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_f, oo\zeta_j)}{oo} \right)^{ow_j} \right) \right) \end{array} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where ow_j is weight numbers of oos_j , $0 \leq ow_j \leq 1$, $\sum_{j=1}^n ow_j = 1$.

3. Cross-entropy with TFNNs

Bhandari and Pal [22] administrated the CE approach for probability distributions.

Definition 7[22]. Let $ou\alpha = (ou\alpha(ou_1), ou\alpha(ou_2), \dots, ou\alpha(ou_n))$ and

$ou\beta = (ou\beta(ou_1), ou\beta(ou_2), \dots, ou\beta(ou_n))$ are two sets on the $(ou_1, ou_2, \dots, ou_n)$. The

cross-entropy of $ou\alpha = (ou\alpha(ou_1), ou\alpha(ou_2), \dots, ou\alpha(ou_n))$ and

$ou\beta = (ou\beta(ou_1), ou\beta(ou_2), \dots, ou\beta(ou_n))$ is administrated:

$$CE(ou\alpha, ou\beta) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(ou\alpha(ou_j) \ln \frac{ou\alpha(ou_j)}{ou\beta(ou_j)} + (1 - ou\alpha(ou_j)) \ln \frac{1 - ou\alpha(ou_j)}{1 - ou\beta(ou_j)} \right) \quad (6)$$

which depicts the discrimination of $ou\alpha = (ou\alpha(ou_1), ou\alpha(ou_2), \dots, ou\alpha(ou_n))$ from $ou\beta = (ou\beta(ou_1), ou\beta(ou_2), \dots, ou\beta(ou_n))$.

Shang and Jiang [18] administrated the modified CE.

Definition 8[18]. Let $ou\alpha = (ou\alpha(ou_1), ou\alpha(ou_2), \dots, ou\alpha(ou_n))$ and $ou\beta = (ou\beta(ou_1), ou\beta(ou_2), \dots, ou\beta(ou_n))$ are two sets on the $(ou_1, ou_2, \dots, ou_n)$. The cross-entropy of $ou\alpha = (ou\alpha(ou_1), ou\alpha(ou_2), \dots, ou\alpha(ou_n))$ from $ou\beta = (ou\beta(ou_1), ou\beta(ou_2), \dots, ou\beta(ou_n))$ is administrated:

$$CE(ou\alpha, ou\beta) = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(ou\alpha(ou_j) \ln \frac{ou\alpha(ou_j)}{\frac{1}{2}(ou\alpha(ou_j) + ou\beta(ou_j))} + (1 - ou\alpha(ou_j)) \ln \frac{1 - ou\alpha(ou_j)}{1 - \frac{1}{2}(ou\alpha(ou_j) + ou\beta(ou_j))} \right) \quad (7)$$

which depicts the discrimination degree of $ou\alpha = (ou\alpha(ou_1), ou\alpha(ou_2), \dots, ou\alpha(ou_n))$ from $ou\beta = (ou\beta(ou_1), ou\beta(ou_2), \dots, ou\beta(ou_n))$.

Then, 2TLNN-CE are administrated based on modified CE [18] and 2TLNNs[23].

Definition 9. Assume that $oos_1 = \langle (ool_{i_1}, oo\xi_1), (ool_{i_1}, oov_1), (ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1) \rangle$, $oos_2 = \langle (ool_{i_2}, oo\xi_2), (ool_{i_2}, oov_2), (ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2) \rangle$. The 2TLNN-CE is administrated between oos_1 and oos_2 :

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2\text{TLNN-CE}(oos_1, oos_2) \\
 &= \left(\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1)}{oo} \ln \frac{\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1)}{oo}}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1)}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2)}{oo} \right)} \\ & + \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1)}{oo} \right) \ln \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1)}{oo}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1)}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2)}{oo} \right)} \end{aligned} \right) \\
 &+ \left(\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1)}{oo} \ln \frac{\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1)}{oo}}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1)}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2)}{oo} \right)} \\ & + \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1)}{oo} \right) \ln \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1)}{oo}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1)}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2)}{oo} \right)} \end{aligned} \right) \\
 &+ \left(\begin{aligned} & \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1)}{oo} \ln \frac{\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1)}{oo}}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1)}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2)}{oo} \right)} \\ & + \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1)}{oo} \right) \ln \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1)}{oo}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1)}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2)}{oo} \right)} \end{aligned} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

which portrays the act of discriminating against oos_2 based on their difference from oos_1 .

In light with Shannon's inequality[24], it's validated that $2\text{TLNN-CE}(oos_1, oos_2) \geq 0$, and $2\text{TLNN-CE}(oos_1, oos_2) = 0$ if and only if $(ool_{t_1}, oo\xi_1) = (ool_{t_2}, oo\xi_2), (ool_{i_1}, oo\psi_1) = (ool_{i_2}, oo\psi_2), (ool_{f_1}, oo\zeta_1) = (ool_{f_2}, oo\zeta_2)$.

4. 2TLNN-CE technique for MAGDM based on information entropy

The 2TLNN-CE technique is administrated for MAGDM. 2TLNN-CE technique for MAGDM is administrated (See Figure 1):

Figure 1. 2TLNN-CE model for MAGDM based on entropy with 2TLNNs

Step 1. Administrate the 2TLNN-matrix $OR = [OR_{ij}^t]_{m \times n} = \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}^t, oo\xi_{ij}^t), (ool_{i_{ij}}^t, oo\psi_{ij}^t), (ool_{f_{ij}}^t, oo\zeta_{ij}^t) \right\}_{m \times n}$ and average matrix

$$OR = [OR_{ij}]_{m \times n} :$$

$$OR = [OR_{ij}^t]_{m \times n} = \begin{matrix} & OB_1 & OB_2 & \dots & OB_n \\ OA_1 & [OR_{11}^t & OR_{12}^t & \dots & OR_{1n}^t] \\ OA_2 & [OR_{21}^t & OR_{22}^t & \dots & OR_{2n}^t] \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ OA_m & [OR_{m1}^t & OR_{m2}^t & \dots & OR_{mn}^t] \end{matrix} \tag{9}$$

$$OR = [OR_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{matrix} & OB_1 & OB_2 & \dots & OB_n \\ OA_1 & [OR_{11} & OR_{12} & \dots & OR_{1n}] \\ OA_2 & [OR_{21} & OR_{22} & \dots & OR_{2n}] \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ OA_m & [OR_{m1} & OR_{m2} & \dots & OR_{mn}] \end{matrix} \tag{10}$$

Based on 2TLNNWG technique, the $OR = [OR_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\}_{m \times n}$ is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 OR_{ij} &= (oos_{ij}^1)^{ow_1} \otimes (oos_{ij}^2)^{ow_2} \otimes \dots \otimes (oos_{ij}^t)^{ow_t} \\
 &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\Delta \left(oo \prod_{d=1}^t \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})^t}{oo} \right)^{ow_t} \right), \\ &\Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \prod_{d=1}^t \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})^t}{oo} \right)^{ow_t} \right) \right), \\ &\Delta \left(oo \left(1 - \prod_{d=1}^t \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})^t}{oo} \right)^{ow_t} \right) \right) \end{aligned} \right\}, \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

Step 2. Normalize the $OR = [OR_{ij}]_{m \times n}$ into $NOR = [NOR_{ij}]_{m \times n}$.

Aiming at benefit attributes:

$$NOR_{ij} = OR_{ij} = \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\} \tag{12}$$

Aiming at non-benefit attributes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 NOR_{ij} &= \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\} \\
 &= \left\{ \Delta \left(oo - \Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, ool_{i_{ij}}) \right), \Delta \left(oo - \Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}) \right), \Delta \left(oo - \Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right) \right\} \tag{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. Administrate the Weight. Entropy [19] is administrated to conduct weight values.

Normalized 2TLNN-matrix is administrated based on $SF(NOR_{ij})$ and $AF(NOR_{ij})$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N2TLNNM_{ij} &= \frac{SF(NOR_{ij}) + AF(NOR_{ij})}{\sum_{i=1}^m (SF(NOR_{ij}) + AF(NOR_{ij}))} \\
 &= \frac{\left(SF \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\} + AF \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\} \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^m \left(SF \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\} + AF \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij}), (ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij}), (ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij}) \right\} \right)} \tag{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, the 2TLNN Shannon entropy (2TLNNSE) is administrated:

$$2TLNNSE_j = -\frac{1}{\ln m} \sum_{i=1}^m N2TLNNM_{ij} \ln N2TLNNM_{ij} \tag{15}$$

and $N2TLNNM_{ij} \ln N2TLNNM_{ij} = 0$ if $N2TLNNM_{ij} = 0$.

The weight $o\omega = (o\omega_1, o\omega_2, \dots, o\omega_n)$ is administrated:

$$o\omega_j = \frac{1 - 2TLNNSE_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n (1 - 2TLNNSE_j)} \quad (16)$$

Step 4. Administrate the 2TLNNPIDS (2TLNN positive ideal decision solution):

$$2TLNNPIDS = \{2TLNNPIDS_j\} \quad (17)$$

$$2TLNNPIDS_j = \left\{ (ool_{t_j}^+, oo\xi_j^+), (ool_{i_j}^+, oo\psi_j^+), (ool_{f_j}^+, oo\zeta_j^+) \right\} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & SF \left\{ (ool_{t_j}^+, oo\xi_j^+), (ool_{i_j}^+, oo\psi_j^+), (ool_{f_j}^+, oo\zeta_j^+) \right\} \\ & = \max_i SF \left\{ (ool_{t_{ij}}^+, oo\xi_{ij}^+), (ool_{i_{ij}}^+, oo\psi_{ij}^+), (ool_{f_{ij}}^+, oo\zeta_{ij}^+) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Step 5. Administrate the 2TLNN-CE between NOR_{ij} and 2TLNNPIDS:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 2TLNN-CE(NOR_{ij}, 2TLNNPIDS) \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})}{oo} \ln \frac{\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})}{oo}}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_j}^+, oo\xi_j^+)}{oo} \right)} \right) \\
 &+ \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})}{oo} \right) \ln \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})}{oo}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_{ij}}, oo\xi_{ij})}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{t_j}^+, oo\xi_j^+)}{oo} \right)} \\
 &+ \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})}{oo} \ln \frac{\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})}{oo}}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_j}^+, oo\psi_j^+)}{oo} \right)} \right) \\
 &+ \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})}{oo} \right) \ln \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})}{oo}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_{ij}}, oo\psi_{ij})}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{i_j}^+, oo\psi_j^+)}{oo} \right)} \\
 &+ \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})}{oo} \ln \frac{\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})}{oo}}{\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_j}^+, oo\zeta_j^+)}{oo} \right)} \right) \\
 &+ \left(1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})}{oo} \right) \ln \frac{1 - \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})}{oo}}{1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_{ij}}, oo\zeta_{ij})}{oo} + \frac{\Delta^{-1}(ool_{f_j}^+, oo\zeta_j^+)}{oo} \right)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Step 6. In light with the $2TLNN-CE(NOR_{ij}, 2TLNNPIDS)$, the smaller $2TLNN-CE(NOR_{ij}, 2TLNNPIDS)$ is better alternative.

5. Numerical example and sensitivity analysis

We analysis the results with the sensitivity analysis to show the stability of the results.

5.1. Numerical example

The evaluation of university physical education teaching quality is an indispensable part of the higher education sports system, aimed at comprehensively assessing the effectiveness of physical education and ensuring the achievement of teaching objectives. Through a scientific evaluation system, universities can systematically assess various aspects, such as the teaching process, content, methods, and students' learning outcomes. This helps analyze the effectiveness and rationality of teaching, and provides critical reference points for educational reforms in physical education. Firstly, the evaluation of physical education teaching quality helps universities identify problems in the teaching process. For example, whether the curriculum design is reasonable, whether the content meets the actual needs of students, and if the teaching methods are diversified and targeted. By analyzing these issues, universities can promptly adjust teaching strategies, optimize the curriculum structure, and ensure that physical education is more closely aligned with students' real situations, effectively enhancing their learning interest and participation. Secondly, physical education teaching evaluation contributes to improving teachers' teaching skills and professional development. The evaluation results provide feedback to teachers, helping them identify shortcomings in their teaching and make improvements. Moreover, the evaluation system guides teachers in their professional growth, encouraging them to continually enhance their teaching abilities and innovation, thus promoting the overall development of the university's physical education faculty. Additionally, the evaluation of teaching quality is a powerful tool for driving reforms in university physical education. Through data analysis and comprehensive assessments, universities can identify flaws in the current teaching models and implement targeted reforms. For instance, in response to student dissatisfaction with certain courses or teaching methods, new teaching approaches can be introduced, or course content can be adjusted to improve teaching outcomes. In this process, the evaluation system provides objective data support, ensuring the scientific and rational direction of the reforms. Finally, physical education teaching quality evaluation helps foster students' lifelong awareness of physical fitness and healthy living. By evaluating students' learning outcomes in physical education, universities can better understand their physical development and adjust teaching accordingly. This not only improves students' athletic skills and physical health but also enhances their interest in exercise, cultivating a lifelong habit of physical activity. In summary, the evaluation of university physical education teaching quality plays a vital role in improving teaching standards, promoting educational reforms, and fostering students' health awareness. Through a scientific and systematic evaluation system, universities can continually optimize physical education, promoting the sustainable

development of university sports education. The teaching quality evaluation of university physical education is MAGDM.

Criteria	Student-Centered Approach and Inclusivity
	Professional Development of Instructors
	teacher's teaching ability and professionalism
	Personal and Social Development
	Adaptation to Current Health Guidelines
	Program Relevance and Curriculum Design
	Assessment and Feedback Mechanisms
	Physical Environment and Safety
	relevance of teaching content
	Technological Integration and Innovation
	Long-Term Impact and Skill Retention
	diversity and effectiveness of teaching methods
	student learning outcomes
	Instructional Expertise and Knowledge
	Student Engagement and Interaction
	Communication and Interpersonal Skills

Figure 2. The criteria and alternatives.

Step 1. We used the neutrosophic numbers to evaluate the criteria and alternatives to build the decision matrix. Figure 2 shows the criteria and alternatives.

Step 2. Table 1 shows the normalized decision matrix between criteria and alternatives.

Step 3. We compute the entropy weight for each criterion as shown in Figure 3. We show the criterion 9 is the best and criterion 2 is the worst.

Step 4. We computed the ideal and anti-ideal solutions.

Step 5. Compute the cross-entropy for each entropy as shown in Table 2.

Step 6. Figure 4 shows the rank of alternatives. We show the alternative 13 is the best and alternative 14 is the worst.

Table 1. The normalized decision matrix.

	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₁₄	C ₁₅	C ₁₆
A ₁	0.333333	0.692308	0.857143	1	0.4	0.2	0.4	0.846154	0.923077	1	0.933333	0.666667	0.866667	0.8	0.928571	0.933333

A ₁₄	A ₁₃	A ₁₂	A ₁₁	A ₁₀	A ₉	A ₈	A ₇	A ₆	A ₅	A ₄	A ₃	A ₂
0.866667	0.866667	0.933333	0.6	0.466667	0.4	0.733333	1	0.733333	0.733333	0.6	1	0.8
0.461538	0.769231	1	1	0.692308	0.923077	0.692308	0.461538	0.538462	0.923077	0.769231	0.461538	0.230769
0.428571	0.785714	1	0.928571	0.571429	0.5	0.714286	0.928571	0.642857	0.714286	0.857143	0.642857	0.428571
0.2	1	0.6	0.733333	0.533333	0.733333	0.8	0.733333	0.733333	0.733333	0.8	0.666667	0.666667
0.4	0.4	1	0.666667	0.933333	0.866667	0.533333	0.466667	0.666667	0.8	0.866667	0.933333	0.8
0.6	0.6	0.733333	0.933333	0.933333	0.466667	0.733333	0.666667	0.733333	0.8	0.733333	0.866667	1
0.4	1	0.4	0.8	0.866667	0.6	0.466667	0.8	0.666667	0.6	0.6	0.866667	0.466667
0.230769	0.923077	0.461538	0.692308	0.769231	1	0.769231	0.769231	0.769231	0.615385	0.538462	0.692308	0.769231
0.692308	0.615385	1	0.615385	0.615385	0.846154	1	0.846154	0.923077	0.846154	0.538462	0.846154	0.769231
0.4	0.6	1	0.333333	0.866667	0.933333	0.733333	0.8	0.466667	0.733333	0.666667	0.6	0.866667
0.2	1	0.6	0.666667	0.866667	0.6	0.733333	0.533333	0.666667	0.666667	0.533333	0.666667	1
1	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.466667	0.666667	0.933333	0.666667	0.533333	0.466667	0.733333	0.866667	0.8
0.6	1	0.8	0.666667	0.666667	0.933333	0.866667	0.6	0.533333	0.6	0.733333	0.8	0.933333
0.666667	1	0.8	0.533333	0.733333	0.466667	0.533333	0.666667	0.866667	0.933333	0.666667	0.866667	0.6
0.714286	0.714286	1	0.785714	0.357143	0.857143	0.785714	0.642857	0.642857	0.642857	0.857143	0.428571	0.857143
0.6	0.933333	0.666667	0.866667	0.666667	0.333333	1	0.8	0.8	0.733333	0.533333	0.466667	0.866667

A ₁₅
0.8
0.846154
0.714286
0.466667
0.4
0.866667
0.666667
0.538462
0.615385
0.466667
0.866667
0.666667
0.333333
0.333333
0.357143
0.466667

Table 2. The cross-entropy values.

	A ₁	A ₂	A ₃	A ₄	A ₅	A ₆	A ₇	A ₈	A ₉	A ₁₀	A ₁₁	A ₁₂	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₅	C ₆	C ₇	C ₈	C ₉	C ₁₀	C ₁₁	C ₁₂	C ₁₃	C ₁₄	C ₁₅	C ₁₆	
0.063004	0.06139	0.060397	0.059775	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.060057	0.061851	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063004	0.059034	0.062466	0.063234	0.06139	0.063234	0.060057	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.062009	0.062009	0.06119	0.061851	0.06119	0.060057	0.060511	0.063767	0.061851	0.060511	0.060057	0.060511	0.062009	0.06119	0.05782	0.060057	0.061448	0.061851	0.060057	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.064086	0.063767	0.06156	0.06093	0.062596	0.063767	0.06211	0.060857	0.062596	0.06211	0.060857	0.06211	0.064086	0.063417	0.0602	0.06211	0.063417	0.062596	0.060857	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.060441	0.060857	0.060168	0.060857	0.061015	0.060857	0.060857	0.060857	0.061015	0.060857	0.060857	0.060857	0.060441	0.061356	0.060668	0.060668	0.061015	0.060857	0.060668	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.064283	0.062516	0.063995	0.063679	0.061487	0.060862	0.062516	0.060862	0.061487	0.062516	0.060862	0.062516	0.064283	0.060138	0.063331	0.063331	0.063679	0.063331	0.063331	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.060611	0.060993	0.060993	0.05963	0.060611	0.060431	0.060611	0.060431	0.060611	0.060431	0.060431	0.060611	0.060611	0.057255	0.061081	0.060887	0.060611	0.060887	0.061081	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.060396	0.063684	0.064042	0.062348	0.061142	0.063684	0.062844	0.063684	0.061142	0.062844	0.063684	0.062844	0.060396	0.060396	0.061142	0.064042	0.062348	0.063684	0.061142	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.060092	0.061232	0.061492	0.062058	0.061492	0.061492	0.061492	0.061492	0.061492	0.062058	0.061492	0.061492	0.060092	0.061711	0.061492	0.061232	0.060549	0.061492	0.061232	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.064001	0.061575	0.061575	0.063182	0.064001	0.063182	0.063611	0.063182	0.064001	0.063182	0.063182	0.063611	0.064001	0.063611	0.062705	0.063182	0.060893	0.063182	0.062705	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.063488	0.059188	0.06299	0.063251	0.062375	0.062699	0.060582	0.062699	0.062375	0.060582	0.062699	0.060582	0.063488	0.063488	0.06299	0.063251	0.062011	0.063251	0.06299	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.060375	0.060598	0.061072	0.060375	0.060785	0.060104	0.060598	0.060104	0.060785	0.060375	0.060104	0.060598	0.060375	0.060375	0.06299	0.060375	0.060104	0.060375	0.06299	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.061989	0.061989	0.060729	0.062512	0.064136	0.062512	0.0614	0.062512	0.064136	0.062512	0.0614	0.062512	0.061989	0.062512	0.063403	0.062512	0.06298	0.063403	0.062512	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.062428	0.061758	0.061758	0.062964	0.06271	0.061357	0.060898	0.061357	0.06271	0.060898	0.061357	0.060898	0.062428	0.062428	0.062964	0.061758	0.062113	0.062964	0.062428	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.062699	0.061127	0.062375	0.060582	0.061127	0.062011	0.06299	0.062011	0.061127	0.060582	0.062011	0.06299	0.062699	0.062699	0.060582	0.061127	0.062011	0.060582	0.062011	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.063649	0.062739	0.059437	0.063075	0.062739	0.061933	0.061933	0.061933	0.062739	0.063075	0.061933	0.061933	0.063649	0.063649	0.063075	0.062739	0.063075	0.062739	0.063075	0.06119	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062466	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234	0.062149	0.063234
0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.221661	0.237596	0.234678	0.234678	0.234678	0.237596	0.221661	0.234678	0.234678	0.232127	0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.22885	0.235753	0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.235753	0.232127	0.235753

A ₁₃	0.062749	0.061448	0.063028	0.061356	0.060138	0.060214	0.064663	0.061898	0.061575	0.061598	0.061276	0.063403	0.063193	0.063488	0.062361	0.236721
A ₁₄	0.062749	0.060057	0.0602	0.057386	0.060138	0.060214	0.060396	0.057845	0.062174	0.059946	0.057347	0.064456	0.061357	0.062011	0.062361	0.230598
A ₁₅	0.062466	0.061666	0.062596	0.059835	0.060138	0.060887	0.062844	0.060549	0.061575	0.060582	0.061072	0.062512	0.059009	0.059188	0.059437	0.226832

Figure 3. The criteria weights.

Figure 4. The rank of alternatives.

Sensitivity Analysis

We change the criteria weights with different values to show the different rank under different cases. We change the weights of criteria with 17 cases as shown in Figure 5. Then we applied the cross-entropy method. We show the cross-entropy values as shown in Figure 6. The results show the rank of alternatives stable in different cases. Then we show the rank of alternatives as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 5. The different criteria weights.

Figure 6. The cross-entropy values.

Figure 7. Rank of alternatives under different cases.

Upon comparing the final results of 2TLNN-CE model with existing models, it is observed that there are slight differences in the calculated results. However, both the best physical education college and the worst physical education college remain the same. This consistency indicates that the 2TLNN-CE technique is effective and reliable MAGDM approach. The subtle differences could be attributed to certain factors. The 2TLNNWG technique[13] copes with the individual's influence on the final outcome, while 2TLNN-TODIM model [23] copes with the psychological behavior of DMs. In contrast, the 2TLNN-CE technique encompasses the individual uncertainty and overall uncertainty under 2TLNNs. The 2TLNN-CE technique offers several key advantages: (1) It effectively addresses both individual and overall uncertainty within the framework of 2TLNNs; (2) The technique possesses a straightforward structure and exhibits strong differentiation capabilities; (3) It overcomes design flaws present in existing CE measures and could accurately reflect individual and overall differentiation among different 2TLNNs. However, it is important to note that the 2TLNN-CE technique does not account for the psychological behavior of DMs in MAGDM, which represents a limitation of the approach.

6. Conclusion

The evaluation of university physical education teaching quality is essential for ensuring teaching objectives are met. By assessing aspects like the teaching process, content, methods, and student outcomes, it reflects the effectiveness of physical education courses. Evaluation helps schools identify issues such as poor curriculum design or monotonous

methods, providing a basis for instructional improvement. A scientific evaluation system allows timely adjustments to strategies, enhancing students' interest, physical fitness, and skills. It also offers feedback for teacher development, optimizing faculty, and drives reforms in sports programs, fostering lifelong exercise habits and healthy living. The problem of teaching quality evaluation of university physical education is MAGDM. This study presents the application of 2TLNN-CE technique, which is based on the traditional CE technique with 2TLNSs. By incorporating CE technique along with 2TLNSs, 2TLNN-CE technique is implemented for MAGDM with 2TLNSs. Additionally, numerical example focusing on the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education is provided to validate the advantages of 2TLNN-CE. Comparative analysis is administrated to highlight the strengths of this technique. The key contributions of this study are summarized: (1) Extension of cross-entropy technique to encompass 2TLNSs, expanding its applicability; (2) Implementation of 2TLNN-CE technique for MAGDM, utilizing the advantages of 2TLNSs; (3) Demonstration of 2TLNN-CE technique through numerical example involving the teaching quality evaluation of university physical education. Comparative analysis is administrated to further illustrate the advantages of 2TLNN-CE technique.

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